

BY IZAN ARAUJO

THE WAR IN UKRAINE AND ITS IMPACT ON GLOBAL BUSINESS: THE CASE OF THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

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How is the War in Ukraine affecting global business, including the automotive industry? The conflict has impacted not only geopolitics but also the global economy, with its effects being felt in the operations of companies. Moreover, on March 3, 2022, the board of directors of the Volkswagen Group AG decided to stop vehicle production in Russia and suspended exports as well. Other automakers, such as Ford and Renault, did the same. The organizations must be antifragile to face geopolitical risks like the war in Ukraine, because it has massively impacted the automotive sector, causing supply chain disruptions, global inflation, and economic sanctions.

First of all, the war caused disruptions in global supply chains. Indeed, Ukraine is an important supplier of noble gases, including neon, which are essential for manufacturing semiconductor chips. The country supplies about 50% of the world's neon gas. In addition, the company Iceblinck, headquartered in Odessa, a port city in Ukraine, exported 65% of the world's neon supply. However, the naval blockade in the Black Sea imposed by Russia had a massive impact on the operation of the port of Odessa, interrupting maritime transport in that region, leading to delays in vehicle production for automakers.

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Second, the sanctions significantly influenced global inflation. In fact, the war resulted in increases in oil prices due to economic sanctions imposed on Russia, the world's third-largest oil producer, behind the United States and Saudi Arabia. In January 2022, Russia's total oil production was 11.3 mb/d. By comparison, US total oil production was 17.6 mb/d, while Saudi Arabia produced 12 mb/d. Consequently, oil prices rose from USD 8/bbl to USD 105/bbl after the news, with expectations that sanctions against Russia would harm energy exports. The rise in oil prices, therefore, increased transportation and production costs for automotive companies. Additionally, the sanctions also affected the supply of natural gas from Russia to Europe.

Map 1: Geostrategic Position of the Port of Odessa

Finally, the economic sanctions imposed on Russia are a driving risk. Although the risk matrix places this event in the green quadrant, indicating a very light impact on the global economy, in the cross-impact matrix, it is located in quadrant II, red, as it is a driving risk capable of influencing two other events: global inflation and supply chain disruption. The World Forum, through its Global Risk Report since 2014, emphasizes that risks are not isolated like islands but rather have interconnectedness between them, so the materialization of one event can trigger a series of other risks.

Oil Production and Market Share of Top 10 Countries (2022)

Source: International Energy Agency, 2022.

1. Risk Matrix

1.2 Risk Matrix Legend

Code	Risk	Macro	Object of Study	Matrix
R.22	War in Ukraine	Russia and Eurasia	Russia and Eurasia	
R.11	Global Inflation	Russia and Eurasia	Russia and Eurasia	
R.13	Supply Chain Disruption	Russia and Eurasia	Russia and Eurasia	
R.21	Economic Sanctions	Russia and Eurasia	Russia and Eurasia	

2. Cross Impact Matrix

2.1 Cross Impact Matrix Legend

Code	Risk	Matrix
R.13	Supply Chain Disruption	Red
R.21	Economic Sanctions	Red
R.22	War in Ukraine	Red
R.11	Global Inflation	Orange

Source: Elaborated by author

3. Cross Impact Matrix

3.1 Cross Impact Matrix Legend

Code	Risk	Matrix
R.11	Global Inflation	Orange
R.13	Supply Chain Disruption	Red
R.21	Economic Sanctions	Red
R.22	War in Ukraine	Maroon

Source: Elaborated by the author

In summary, the four risks discussed in this policy brief demonstrated the importance of the board of directors and also CEOs of organizations to pay attention not only to the criticality of risks but particularly to their motricity. Clearly, understanding this interconnectedness is essential to develop effective prevention and mitigation measures. Based on the prioritization matrix, we recommend as a response to risks that automakers affected by the war perform prospective scenario analyses to adapt their business strategies to different geopolitical events, such as the war in Ukraine and supply chain disruption, ensuring their resilience and antifragility.

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